

DIRECTIVE LEADERSHIP: A CONCEPTUAL REASSESSMENT THROUGH A BIBLIOGRAPHIC REVIEW

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Abstract

Directive leadership is a conception that has been gaining more prominence in the various current pedagogical formulations, due to the encouraging results that it has presented in different investigations. The present study used the bibliographic review as a research method due to its ability to systematize information from different virtual sources. The results expressed that the concept of directive leadership is in an early application stage, due to the small number of productions found. It is concluded that directive leadership is a concept of vital importance for the progress of the educational institution due to the involvement that the director has under this perspective is that of a guide and mentor, exceeding the bureaucratic conception which was assigned in preliminary years.

Keywords: Directive Leadership, Education, Literature Review

INTRODUCTION

Education is considered one of the most important and conflictive conceptions of the human, due to its dynamic character, it must be constantly updated before new scenarios, trends and paradigms that are emerging within educational science (Rubio, 2007). One of them is found within the school organizational structure itself, which initially was only composed of teachers and a student, through generation this conformation was expanded considerably until today.

The irruption of bureaucratic development of institutions in the 19th century brought about a new model of educational institution, dehumanized from its previous conceptions. In this new model, coexisting alongside the classical dynamics developed in the classrooms, we are talking about the administrative unit of the institution. The staff in charge of running this unit was the director of the institution, which was considerably deprived of its educational role. (Maureria Cabrera, 2018).

Due to the fact that one of the competencies that the director of an educational institution must have been his or her condition as is its leading status. Given that leadership is composed of a set of processes that guide users and collectives in a certain direction, which are the goals proposed by the stakeholders. Similarly, this process must provide the community with constant learning through artefacts that encourage this process (Pozner, 2000)

In the 21st century, exercising the role of the school principal in terms of leadership has required efficient professional and pedagogical competencies (Vaillant & Marcelo, 2009; Bolívar, 2010). However, principals spend a large number of working hours on administrative duties and the supervision of human resources (OCDE, 2009). This considerably limits the development of pedagogical and leadership skills, which are of vital importance for the progress of the educational institution they head. This is due to the fact that monitoring and evaluation of learning progress, as well as overseeing the teachers' development are increasingly less frequent activities (UNESCO, 2008). So, the report *The Teaching and Learning International Survey* (TALIS) of the

Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (2019), states that there are enormous possibilities to improve the working and pedagogical conditions of teachers, thus, improving the learning processes of students.

So, an educational leadership must have, according to Maya, Aldana, Zavala and Isea (2018, p.116), endowments of being “a good motivator, guide and mediator in situations, conflicts, within the school, looking for the employee satisfaction and the well-being of itself”. Similarly, Farre Martí (2002, p. 125) argues that directive leadership “is the task distinguished by standard-setting, the organization of work and concentration on goals, it is very effective in keeping a group focused on a mission”. Likewise, this capacity makes mention of an “actor who initially requests the opinion of subordinate and gives detailed instructions of how, when and where they should carry out a specific task to solve a problem” (Simbrón-Espejo & Sanabria-Boudri, 2019, p.63).

One of the purposes of implementing this type of leadership is to encourage a substantial improvement in teaching performance. Because this activity is a fundamental factor in educational quality since the teaching performance is composed of three fundamental elements which are professional training, academic preparation, motivation and creativity, with the goal of achieving acceptable results in their work activity. (Escribano, 2018). Similarly, directive leadership encourages school managers to implement democratic dynamics with a view to forging a committed leadership with the professional and personal development of teachers (Leithwood, 2006).

Have been developed different classifications of this style of leadership among which we can mention the segregation made by Sergiovanni (2001, p.47)

Table 1: Types of Leaders according to Sergiovanni (2001)

Type of Leader	Definition
Technical lead	Responsible for planning, organizing, coordinating and establishing the organizational structures to ensure optimum efficiency in the institution
Humanist leader	It focuses on human relations, interpersonal competence and instrumental motivation techniques. Supports, encourages and provides professional development opportunities for members of the institution.
Educational leader	Responsible for developing educational and clinical supervision programs, diagnoses educational problems, orients teachers, promoting the supervision, assessment and is concerned with curriculum development
Symbolic leader	The one who assumes the role of head and pays attention to the selection of goals and important behaviours on the campus. Tours the institution, visit the classrooms, maintains direct and permanent contact with students, and establishes priorities in educational interests.
Cultural leader	Responsible for defining, strengthening and articulating the values, beliefs and cultural roots that give the school its unique identity. Articulate the mission of the institution, maintain traditions, socialize with the members of the community to the culture of the school and develop and manifest a system of symbols over the years that reflects school culture.

Source: Calero (2005)

Studies by Mourshed et al. (2010) and Barber and Mourshed (2007), deduce that academic performance according to PISA and TIMSS tests, in educational institutions that have shown great progress in their results, has a strong school leadership present in the principals. Likewise, it is to be considered that “The work of principals and school leaders has been indicated as the second most determinant intra-school factor, after

teaching, in student learning” (Weinstein, Muñoz & Fless, 2019: 10). However, Valli (2015), points out that there is an insufficient quantity of research regarding the above, so it has not been possible to infer in its entirety the correlation relationship that this leadership has with educational development.

Nevertheless, the role of the principal is one of the topics that has received the least attention in scientific research in the educational field, since other educational aspects have gained greater prominence. Consequently, one of the limitations of this documentation is due to the limited supply of research published in indexed journals of Latin American origin, which does not exceed 1% of the totality of educational topics (Aravena y Hallinger, 2018). Therefore, this research will choose to carry out a brief diagnosis of this statement.

According to the above, emerges question, what is the status of the researcher that has an affinity with the reformulation of the concept of directive leadership in education? For this reason, this research aims to analyse elucidations and own experiences of directive leadership in the period from 2015 to 2020.

METHOD

To give methodological consistency to the study carried out, it was used the qualitative approach, and the method employed was the bibliographic review, which is intended to investigate, collect, organize, analyse and interpret information on a theme (Alfonso, 1995). It should be added that the mission of this type of research lies in making knowledge viable, with the task of patenting a relevant state of the art about a particular area of science (Perestelo-Pérez, 2013).

The procedure to be followed began with the selection of research from the main databases, based on the formulas described below. After that, we proceeded to understand them by means of a documentary analysis technique through the use of a bibliographic manager. It is important to consider Bobenrieth (1994), who states that this type of journal is characterized by its clarity, conciseness, precision and simplicity. The literature was selected according to inclusion and exclusion criteria, to specify the works chosen. Likewise, these documents are within five years prior to the implementation of the journal, to obtain an updated judgement of this concept.

First phase: Search strategy and general review

Within this stage corresponding to the recovery and selection, it was established defined parameters, such as search engines and equations, and inclusion and exclusion criteria, which are presented below:

Database and search equations

The collection of the documents was carried out from an exhausting search in different databases, as explained by Gil (1994, p.4) “a file of interrelated data, collected, that satisfy the information needs of a given community of users”. The following database was used for the present research: a) Google Scholar, b) Scopus, c) Scielo, d) Dialnet

In addition, to recover the information from the aforementioned databases, keywords were defined for the bibliographic search (Creswell, 2014). They allowed us to elaborate the search equations, using the indications developed by Merino-Trujillo (2011). Consequently, it was possible to define two search equations, which are composed of 5 individual terms, which cooperated to configure the study variable A*=

(Table 2). It should also be mentioned that the search equations were made up of special characters that fulfilled their purpose of refining the search.

- Quotation marks were used to define the more specific terms of the subject matter addressed.
- The code “AND”, “AND” OR “+” was used to add two subjects and make a conjunction
- The term “OR” was used to indicate to the search engine that it can make a selection of one term or another.

Table 2: Table of concepts

A*
The directive leadership and educational development
The directive leadership +Latin America
The “directive leadership”

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Once the databases and search equations had been selected, these allows us to do an adequate search of fields; the next step was to establish inclusion and exclusion criteria that give us the ability to select the literature to be reviewed (Manzano & García, 2016).

It is of great importance to recognize that for this collection of information was established a timescale of analysis, which is comprised between the years 2015-2021. The inclusion and exclusion criteria are shown in table 2.

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Studies with ● Elaborated in the period 2015-2021 ● Studies related to the directive leadership and education ● Studies in the current format 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Publications before the year 2015 ● English documents

Information processing

The selected documents were processed using handcrafted techniques of content analysis, using the Stylist tool which allows the recognition of the most frequently used words in the selected works. Likewise, it was used a bibliographic card for the appropriate systematization of the information collected.

RESULTS

Then, it will be shown the 18 selected papers, which have been selected using the inclusion and exclusion criteria mentioned above. Therefore, this data will be exposed through a matrix that will show the main characteristics of each one of them.

Table 3: Documents related

No	Year	Author	Title	Country of origin
1	2015	Vaillant	School leadership, evolution and practices and improvement of educational quality	Uruguay
2	2016	Furguerle Rangel & Vitorá	Leadership in primary education principals.	Venezuela
3	2017	Arana & Coronado	Directive leadership and teaching performance in a parochial educational institution in San Isidro district.	Peru
4	2017	Cancino & Vera	Educational policies to strengthen directive leadership: challenges for Chile from a comparative analysis with OECD countries	Chile
5	2017	Reyes Romero, Trejo Cázares & Topete Barrera	Directive leadership and management at the upper secondary level of the National Polytechnic Institute of Mexico: a view from the students.	Mexico
6	2018	Maureira Cabrera	Educational leadership practices: A evolutionary and illustrative view based on its main frameworks, dimensions and most representative indicators.	Costa Rica
7	2018	Salvador Cornelio & Sánchez Ortega	The leadership of principals and organizational commitment of Teacher	Peru
8	2019	Franco Arízaga, <i>et al.</i>	Directive leadership as an instrument to promote the empowerment of the Educational Community of Ecuador	Ecuador
9	2020	Incio & Capuñay	Directive leadership and teaching performance in private educational institutions	Peru
10	2020	Gaete Vergara, Acuña Collado & Ramírez Muga	Social leadership, the driving force for management practices in the confinement context	Chile
11	2020	Aparicio Molina <i>et al.</i>	Directive leadership and educational change: analysis of a university-school collaboration experience	Chile
12	2020	Fretes Ayala	Styles of directive leadership in higher education	Mexico
13	2020	Rossi Valverde & Rossi Ortiz	Directive leadership, a model for measuring the construct for application in regular elementary education.	Peru
14	2020	Ruiz Cutipa, Huaranga Rivera, Moscoso Paucarchuco and Flores Moscol	Directive leadership and administrative management of public educational institutions of the initial level UGEL 01 of Lima	Peru
15	2021	Romero	Directive leadership in Schools that Overcome Contextual Barriers.	Argentina
16	2021	Barrientos Velito & Alania Pacovilca	Directive leadership and institutional climate: radiography of private educational institutions in south-eastern Peru.	Peru
17	2021	Córdova Ramírez, Rojas Idrogo & Marín Ruiz	Directive leadership of educational institutions:	
18	2021	Silva Valle	Directive leadership and teaching performance at the "Miguel Cervantes" Basic Education School, cantón Baba-Ecuador- 2021	Peru

Source: Own elaboration

We will proceed to make a brief exposition of the documents mentioned in the previous matrix, we rescue the ideas presented by Reyes Romero Trejo Cázares & Topete Barrera (2017) who through their research concluded that the most demanded characteristics of the students towards the director of their study centre are: interaction with them, responsibility and leadership. Because of this, the authors consider that leadership has a dual notion since it is a competence and a strategy that governs the development of the principal as the main actor of the educational centre. Likewise, the research developed by Maureira Cabrera (2018) explains that this leadership has been considered the most important link within the disaggregation of managerial roles (Directions, coordination, teacher and student leaders). Because administrative management is governed by the principal's manoeuvring, it is assumed that management capacity and the personification of leadership must be intrinsic conditions for this actor.

It should be added to the discussion the work elaborated by Salvador Cornelio & Sánchez Ortega (2018) who through the results obtained from their research deduce that directive leadership generates the right conditions for the organizational commitment of the educational institution. Since this competence generates an atmosphere of solidarity that builds on the work ties that are created in the educational centre. Another strength of directive leadership, it exposes the document prepared by Ruiz Catipa, et al. (2020) who were dedicated to developing correlational research between directive leadership and the administrative management of the institution itself. The results found affirm a high correlation between these two variables, thus elucidating the effectiveness of an efficient development of these work by the institution's principal.

As a result, Romero (2021) shows that directive leadership is a predominant characteristic in principals who have professional training and specializations in management, as well as having worked for more than ten years in the institution, moreover having previous experience in leadership positions and having an affective bond with the school. Similarly, Furguerle & Vitorá (2016), through their research, describe their experience in the primary level educational centre. Where the application of a survey to the institution's staff corroborated that the principal did not possess leadership skills. Because the principal did not frequently practice communication and motivation with the students and teachers of the educational centre. This has caused constant problems within the articulation of the actors of the educational institution and in the educational progress of students. This is expressed in the lack of motivation within the school and work environment, which generates inefficient educational results.

Likewise, the work was done by Barrientos and Pacovilca (2021), who selected educational institutions in Peru to carry out their research project. They found that the principal's educational leadership has a significant relationship with the institutional climate, given the results obtained from the Rho Spearman correlation statistical analysis. Therefore, the authors, based on their experience, recommend its implementation in different educational centres, to generate better environments for educational development in an efficient manner.

We should add the study by Fretes Ayala (2021) who, after making an exhaustive analysis of different positions and approaches to directive leadership, concluded that this condition requires creativity and communication skills in the development of

strategies; all to contribute to the conditions of culture and organizational climate of the educational institution over which presides. In the same way, the document prepared by Arana and Coronado (2017), relates an experience that was carried out in an educational centre where they managed to elucidate the direct relationship found between directive leadership and teaching performance. Therefore, the authors conclude that adequate exercise of this educational competence will generate tangible results in the educational development of students and teachers.

Similarly, Franco Arizaga et al. (2019), conclude after an analysis of the available literature on the case, that directive leadership is awarded the task of empowering all participants in the educational structure. This is achieved through assertive management and interpersonal skills of the principal; it is important to consider that this process is cloistered under governmental guidelines and the demands of society itself. In addition to this, there is the research developed by Rossi Valverde y Rossi Ortiz (2021), who through a factorial analysis was able to elucidate the four dimensions covered by this concept, which are: Strengthen the organization, model the behaviour, motivate employees and consolidate leadership. Another relevant characteristic to be discussed at this stage is the one reported by Ruiz Cutipa et al. (2017), who through a bibliographic review was able to elucidate another facet of the concept of directive leadership. It focuses on the development of distance education.

It would be necessary to add the thesis developed by Silva Valle (2022), which states that the development of the practice of directive leadership, prominent of the school principal, is in tune with the dynamics of socialization that take place among teachers. This is because their leadership is strengthened by a group that is united and supports their decisions and ideas. On the other hand, there is the research developed by Valliant (2015), it is important to highlight that this model is in tune with the formulation and execution of educational policies of each particular nation. Given that this competition is a process that involves different spheres of the educational structure, from the highest pedagogical formulators in the country to the recipients of this proposal, which would be the students.

CONCLUSIONS

The set of studies previously analysed provides us with a vision of the current location of directive leadership through the different experiences and conceptual compilations. This demonstrates the evening interest of researchers in analysing and applying ideas about directive leadership. Likewise, it is important to consider that educational action has been the victim of countless reforms, modifications, and changes in paradigms, to adapt to the new environments and competencies that are more rapidly appearing today.

Within these dynamics, the conceptualization of the educational principal as a leader must go far beyond that of a bureaucratic agent in charge of administrative activities. This actor must be found as the central architect of the pedagogical action carried out in the educational centres, in order to maximize student learning. In this way, to make more efficient strategies that feed the educational practice from their respective instances.

It is to be considered that the implementation of this research method, bibliographic review, has managed to synthesize a considerable number of documents efficiently and clearly. To accelerate future research on the subject, considering that one of the

problems described was the insufficient amount of work on the concept of directive leadership. In this way, the present article is awarded the role of inciting the replicability of these experiences, with the mission of dynamizing the research field corresponding to this stratum of knowledge.

Research such as the one presented above contributes to the accumulation of educational knowledge. Therefore, the optional reflection is located around the reevaluation of this actor within the educational process as a key element to develop a new pedagogical ideology, where more actors are involved to provide the learning with the ideal conditions for its development.

Notes

Competencies, according to Perrenoud (2004:11) is the “faculty to mobilize a set of cognitive resources (knowledge, skills, information, etc.) to solve with relevance and effectiveness a series of situations”. Likewise, the use of professional competencies considerably enhances the educational quality. Especially in the building of an ambivalent stance of the teacher, given that, his work of nourishing knowledge to students, perfects its professional development as an educator (Klieger, 2016; Tanriogen e Iscan, 2016)

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